

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

**External organic matters for climate mitigation and
soil health (EOM4SOIL, EJP-SOIL SP3 internal project)**

Executive summary

Actual submission date: 15.03.2025

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Programme title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Programme website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Project title: External organic matters for climate mitigation and soil health

Project website:

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	Executive summary
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Executive summary
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP7
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Coordination, dissemination and communication
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	Sabine Houot, INRAE
AUTHOR:	
DOI:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15025010
LICENSE	CC BY 4.0
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	PU

Purpose

Many activities generate organic wastes, including housing and urban activities (e.g. biowastes, sewage sludges and green wastes), industries and agriculture (e.g. manures). Such organic matters have been defined as external organic matters (EOM) since not directly issued from the soils where they are applied or transformed during a treatment before their application on soils (anaerobic digestion for example). The recycling of EOM on soils, with or without pre-processing, is strongly encouraged by the Europe Union as part of a Circular Economy. Recycling on soils is however only possible, if application (i) is beneficiary for soils (carbon storage, increased biological activities...) and/or crop production (substitution of fertilizers...); (ii) does not generate environmental impacts through excess contaminant upload, nutrient losses (nitrate leaching for example) or gas emission (N_2O , NH_3 ...). Transformation process before application and EOM application management (dose, period of application, fertilized crop...) could help enhancing the EOM associated benefits while decreasing the trade-off. So, the general objective of the EOM4SOIL project was to propose best management practices of EOM treatment and application for climate change mitigation and soil health improvement, for representative farming systems of arable crops in Europe and considering the diversity of pedoclimatic conditions. More specific objectives were: (i) to assess multiple effects of EOM applications including contaminants; (ii) to evaluate the C balance between C storage and greenhouse gas (GHG) emission including during treatments; (iii) to recommend innovative pre-processing to improve C budget and soil health; (iv) to define best management practices from scenarios of use based on multicriteria simulation tools.

Intended audience

The main results obtained during the EOM4SOIL project should be relevant for:

- **All people involved in the management of EOMs and their use in agriculture** (farmer advisers, waste treatment managers,...) : database of the characteristics of EOMs (WP1), database of long-term experiments dedicated to the use of EOM (WP3), collected results of the most documented long term experiments where EOMs are applied and evaluation/comparison of their multiple effects (WP3), results of long-term simulation of crop succession and actual practices of EOM use by farmers and of the focus groups (WP6) ...
- **People involved in city and territory managements**: results could help them to decide the local policy about urban waste use in agriculture (WP2, WP3, WP6);
- **Policy makers, policy development**: the database of EOM characteristics (WP1), of long-term effects of repeated application of EOMs (WP3), the database and experimental results about contaminants (WP5) should be useful to develop new regulation about EOM use in agriculture together with the results about “new contaminants” such as microplastics (WP5). In addition, the lack of documented references about soil quality (WP3) confirms that such references should be established. The results about GHG budget (C storage, nutrient supply and GHG emissions) should also be really useful (WP6).
- **Future scientific objectives** (scientific policy and needs): The EOM4SOIL project pointed out the lack of information or knowledges missing to fully assess the diversity of effects of EOM use in agriculture (lack of quantitative data, of long-term effects for a large diversity of EOMs, of GHG emission during treatments or in the field after EOM applications).

Description of the main activities

The EOM4SOIL included **3 levels of work** in order to improve knowledge and understanding about EOM use and multiple effects on soil-crop systems to improve the environmental balance of the EOM use in agriculture:

- **EOM:** a first level concerned the EOMs themselves with the characterization of their diversity including physico-chemical characteristics, and the improvement of their treatment before application in order to improve their efficiency;
- **Soil-crop system:** the second level quantified the multiple effects of repeated applications of EOMs and compared them. The long-term experiments with repeated applications of EOM were collected and the data available used to assess their effects on soil and crop quality indices. In addition, a focus on contaminants was added with specific attention to an emergent one, the microplastics. The balance between C storage and GHG emission was also studied together with other emission gas (NH₃ and BVOC);
- **Farmer practices:** Real crop successions including EOM use under European pedoclimatic conditions were simulated to assess the multiple effects after more than 30 years and point out the trade-off between their effect. In addition, interactions with all stakeholders concerned by EOM use in agriculture were realized (Focus groups) to assess the expected results or needs to improve the EOM management in agriculture or to develop the market of their use.

Different approaches/methods were used:

- **Data collection and database elaboration:** in the participating countries, data about EOM characteristics and management were collected. A focus about the long-term field experiments (LTE) studying EOM was constructed based on other LTE gathered within Europe and EJP SOIL (BONARES, ...);
- **Statistical analysis of these databases:** innovative methods were used to develop classes of EOM, to better characterize the effects of repeated applications on soil and crop quality indices;
- **Simulation:** simulation tools were used to assess the long-term effects of EOM applications and the trade-off among effects, for actual crop successions and practices in Europe;
- **Experiments:** experimental results were also assessed during the EOM4SOIL project (improvement of the treatment before their application, new short-term experiments were established to answer new questions or characterized new EOMs, additional assessments in the LTE (about microplastics for example...));
- **Focus groups:** Specific interactions with a large diversity of stakeholders were organized to determine their expected needs and priorities to maintain sustainable use of EOMs in agriculture.

Key results

The major results of EOM4SOIL will be presented by work-packages.

- **EOM diversity (WP1):** A database (available on Zenodo soon) with the characteristics of 122 EOMs was developed. The EOM types were defined based on their initial materials (manure, sewage sludge, green waste...) and the treatment process applied before their application (unprocessed, composting, anaerobic digestion, pyrolysis). The physico-chemical characteristics were collected and pointed out the diversity of these physico-chemical characteristics, the effect of composting (increased dry matter, loss of mineral N, ...), anaerobic digestion (decreased dry matter, increased nitrogen content...). A statistical analysis showed that EOM diversity could be divided in 3 clusters either for their fertilizing or amending values or contaminant contents. However, the clusters differed in the 3 classifications. For example, digestates were in cluster 3 of high fertilizing value and in cluster 1 concerning their amending value. So an interface was developed to visualize the physico-chemical characteristics of all EOM types (average values and variability).

- **The treatments before application make possible to produce more efficient EOMs (WP2):** Specific attention has been given on anaerobic digestion with experimental approaches. The addition of biochar or straw during anaerobic digestion of manure were compared. Straw appeared to be more interesting than biochar with three times more biogas produced during the process. In addition, anaerobic digestion increases nutrient availability in the digestate compared to the untreated inputs. Other recommendations were produced for biochar production and improvement of composting process.
- **Long-term field experiments dedicated to EOM use were collected (WP3):** A detailed inventory of LTE dedicated to the assessment of multiple effects of repeated EOM applications was realized. Specific and more detailed meta data (information) were collected compared to the census realized within BONARES for examples. Information about the EOM applied, the collected information and data over the different years of the experiments were gathered in a database (**available on Zenodo**). 201 LTE were found with a strong heterogeneity in the spatial distribution of LTE (the largest number found in Germany), of EOM tested (farmyard manure largely dominating the LTE). The assessed parameters during the LTE pointed out that the physico-chemical characteristics of soils were mostly followed with organic matter and nutrients mainly, followed by trace elements and much fewer biological activities. For crops, the main results concerned the crop yields and major nutrients. Very few data about organic contaminants are available.
- **The LTE were used to calculate soil and crop quality indices used to compare the EOM effects after repeated applications on arable crops (WP3).** Six indices were defined: carbon storage, soil physical properties, soil fertility, soil biology, soil contaminants and crop productivity. Most indices were improved with EOM applications, except soil contaminants in some cases. When compared to control mineral-fertilized treatments, 4 classes of experimental treatments with EOMs could be characterized by a gradient of most indices (soil carbon storage, crop productivity, soil biology, and soil contaminants). The gradients often varied similarly (more C storage, higher indices of biological activity, of crop productivity...). The classes for soil contaminants slightly differed. In all cases, the main drivers for indices evolutions were the fluxes of elements entering the soils with the EOM treatments (input of organic C, of nutrients, of contaminants...).
- **Databases of gas emission and GHG balance (WP4).** Three sets of data were constructed: (i) a database with N₂O emission measurements in LTE with EOMs. It appeared that the available sets were rather few. N₂O emission factors in field conditions were calculated for a ten years period and varied between 1 and 1.5% of total N applied for EOM and 1 to 2.5% for mineral fertilizer. The balance between C storage and GHG emission in the field remained positive (+0.5 to 1.1 t C/ha.year); (ii) a database with NH₃ emission under field condition but also in laboratory-controlled conditions was also produced; (iii) finally a database with biological volatile organic carbon was also produced.
- **Short-term experiments pointed out the large variability of N₂O and NH₃ emissions after EOM application (WP4).** Biochar addition with other EOMs seemed to decrease the gas emissions.
- **The addition of EOMs increases biological activities** and organic carbon mineralisation in soil but did not modify the Carbon Use efficiency of the microorganisms (**WP4**).
- **The input of contaminants with EOM repeated application represent an important trade-off to the use of EOM (WP5).** Data about contaminants measured in the EOMs were specifically collected together with the different thresholds defined in regulations in the participating countries. Trace elements were mostly assessed. It appeared that in most cases the contaminant levels in EOM used in agriculture were below the maximum thresholds defined in the regulations. In addition, the measured contaminants were only slightly available because of strong retentions in soil. Specific attention was given to microplastics that could

enter the soils with EOM application. It also appeared that microplastics could be leached down in deeper soils.

- **The long-term effects of repeated EOM applications in actual real cropping system and farmer practices were assessed using a multicriteria simulation tool (WP6).** Carbon storage and nutrient saving varied with the cropping system and the used EOM. But globally the **nitrogen saving tended to increase after long-term application** due to the increased soil organic matter (median supply of 17 kgN/year during the first crop succession with the highest supply with pig slurry digestate and lowest with horse manure, increasing up to 50 kgN/year after 30 years of simulation). On the contrary, **carbon storage tended to decrease** with time (median of 390 kg C/ha year stored during the first crop succession with the highest value with cattle manure and lowest with sewage sludge because of the rates of application, decreasing to 70 kgC/ha.year after 30 years of simulation) because of reaching new equilibrium of carbon storage. When considering the GHG budget of these cropping systems, C storage and nutrient saving were larger than GHG emission during the first years of application; however, the GHG balance decreased with time because of the decreased C storage when field GHG emission remained similar. In addition, when GHG emission during EOM treatment before their applications were considered, they decreased the benefits measured in the field.
- **Discussions with stakeholders were organized to define the priorities to be considered for sustainable use of EOM in agriculture (WP6).** The socio-economic aspects appeared as most important including: (i) financial incitation to develop the different value chains for composting, biochar production, anaerobic digestion..., (ii) monetization of the benefits associated to EOM use (C credits, improved soil health...).

Research and technical implications

The EOM application on soils is necessary to ensure nutrient cycling looping. The EOM4SOIL project contributed to the general objective defined at the beginning of the project with recommendations about EOM treatment and EOM application management on cropped soils. Several perspectives were pointed out about future research and technical implications.

- **Several databases** were initiated: (i) **about EOM characteristics.** The database has been constructed based on the origin of the EOM and the treatment applied before EOM use in agriculture with a visualization tool that received very positive returns. This database should be maintained and developed with additional information about EOM characteristics. In addition, information about the availability and the quantification of EOM per country appeared to be missing although it would be very interesting to better quantify the benefits related to their use. (ii) **about GHG emission or ammonia volatilization** after EOM application. Not enough data could be collected to be able to consolidate the prediction of GHG emission or ammonia volatilization. Again, such data collection should be continued; (iii) about parameters measured in LTE testing the application of EOMs. Only 6 LTE offered very detailed results. More references should be collected and for more diversified EOMs.
- **The analysis of multiple effects related with repeated EOM application pointed out the lack of references for the evaluation of soil health and quality.** This confirmed the need of such reference for the monitoring of soil health and quality discussed within the construction of the soil directive at the European level.
- **Analytical references for regulated contaminants showed that the EOM used in agriculture have contaminant contents below the maximum regulated thresholds.** However, question remained for emergent contaminants such as microplastics or others (PFAS for example). Again, to evaluate potential impacts related with new contaminants, the LTE appeared as very important supports.

- **The simulation of scenario of long-term use pointed out that, after many years C storage would stop when reaching equilibrium.** The GHG emission could then become more impacting. And it will be very important to maintain these higher levels of organic C in soils raising out the question of stability of the stored organic carbon. In addition, we pointed out **the important impact of GHG emission during the treatment before application.** Data are missing and such emission should be more controlled.
- The focus group with the stakeholder pointed out that **economic issues are preponderant** for the future of sustainable value chain of EOM (financial support of treatment, monetisation of ecosystem services other than C credits...).
- Finally, all meeting with stakeholders confirmed the need for a better transfer of scientific results in practical advices for EOM management.

Policy implications

No direct policy recommendations were produced during the EOM4SOIL project. However, it produced information and database that should be useful for policy makers. We pointed out that all EOMs used in agriculture had contaminant contents below the thresholds mentioned in regulations. About contaminants, specific attention should be dedicated to new ones such as microplastics which are present in EOMs and measurement in LTE showed that they could be leached in the soil profiles. The multicriteria tools and long-term assessments of multi-effects related to repeated applications showed that EOMs could be used to increase soil C storage with associated increased saving of mineral fertilizers. At the beginning, C storage is larger than GHG emission with a positive balance. But C storage decrease with time because of reaching equilibrium and GHG emission could overpass the benefits of C storage on the long term. In addition, more attention should be given to the entire value chain, including the production or treatment of EOM before their application because of emission during treatments that could compensate the benefits after application on soils. In all cases, a global environmental assessment of EOM use should be made (including treatment and application) with considering alternative use of the EOMs if not applied on soils to conclude on the most interesting use of the EOMs. Finally, the focus groups pointed out that sustainable value chain of EOM use could not exist without economic incentives (direct incentive financial support of the EOM production, monetisation of the benefits after use in agriculture...).

Conclusion

The EOM application on soils is necessary to ensure nutrient cycling looping. EOM4SOIL pointed out through the analysis of LTE results, that benefits were larger than environmental impacts for EOMs used in agriculture. The existing regulations ensure quality improvement of EOM. Future regulation should keep helping the development of sustainable value chain of EOM production and use in agriculture. The long-term use of EOM showed that C storage was observed with increased associated benefits (nutrient saving, biological activities...) without excess trade-off (more GHG emission, excess nutrient leaching, contaminant load...) with a positive environmental balance. Future works should focus both on very long-term use when the new equilibrium would be reached with less C storage and considering the entire value chain (EOM production/treatment and EOM use). In addition, future research should include socio-economic aspects (monetization of benefits, incentive support for treatments...) that appeared to be essential for the stabilization of sustainable use of EOMs.

